

FORENSIC MEDICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SUBSEQUENT ATROPHY IN OPTIC NERVE INJURY

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ANNOTATION

Currently, optic nerve atrophy is not only a problem in modern ophthalmology related to the complexity of early differential diagnosis, severity of damage, and unfavorable prognosis, but also causes significant difficulties in forensic medical examination, including in determining the harm caused to health.

Keywords: Forensic medical examination, injuries.

In practice, it is not always possible to establish the etiology of optic nerve atrophy. However, during a forensic medical examination, establishing a cause-and-effect relationship between trauma and the development of optic nerve atrophy is a crucial task. This pathology is also considered a crucial medical and social problem: optic nerve atrophy occupies one of the leading places among disabling visual disorders, surpassing only glaucoma and degeneration.

Among those who suffered severe eye injuries, 89.9% were men and 10.2% were women. Trauma is more common in young people. The age of 60% of those injured does not exceed 40 years. About 22% of those hospitalized with injuries are children under 16 years of age. Eye symptoms in closed head and brain injuries are frequently observed: according to I. D. Fedorov (1969), in 79% of patients; according to Yu. M. Rodionov (1970), in 85% of patients. In the acute period of trauma, lesions of the optic tract predominate (49.5%), most often - lesions of the chiasm (33%). In second place in frequency are pupillary innervation disorders - 48.5%, with anisocoria predominating - 24%. Damage to the nerves of the oculomotor apparatus is observed in 26.5% of patients, of which damage to the abducting nerve is most common (13.5%). The rarest eye symptoms are exophthalmos (2.6%), complete unilateral ophthalmoplegia (1.5%), optic nerve atrophy (1%), and Purcher's retinitis (0.5%). The incidence of partial optic nerve atrophy in the RF is 0.32 per 10,000, and its specific weight in the overall structure of diseases due to visual impairments is only 0.57 per mille. According to E.J. Tron (1955), the distribution of patients with partial optic nerve atrophy by etiology was as follows: in 40.5% of patients, atrophy developed against the background of CNS diseases; in 13.2% the cause was intoxication; in 12.3% - hypertension and atherosclerosis; in 6.5% - trauma; in 7.4% of cases - other causes; etiology was not detected in 20.4%. M.T. Aznabaev (2001) found that among hospitalized patients with partial optic nerve atrophy, atrophy predominated due to circulatory disorders in the eye's vascular basin - in 28.5% of cases, and due to craniocerebral injuries - in 24.1%). N.A. Shigina (2001) distinguishes the following etiological groups of patients with partial optic nerve atrophy: post-ischemic - 71.4%; post-infectious - 14.2%; post-traumatic - 8.1%; post-intoxication - 1.4%; glaucomatous - 4.9%. Although optic nerve atrophy is a relatively rare complication, its forensic medical significance does not diminish. Optic nerve atrophy is not an independent disease. This is a consequence of various pathological processes affecting various parts of the visual pathway. Clinically, it is characterized by visual impairment (decreased visual acuity, visual field defects), paleness, and a decrease in the optic nerve disc diameter. Depending on the degree of damage to the optic fibers, and consequently, the degree of decreased visual functions and paleness of the optic

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nerve disc, initial or partial and complete atrophy of the optic nerve are distinguished. Post-traumatic optic nerve atrophy results from severe contusions of the orbit or eyeball (retrobulbar hematoma), significant hemorrhages in orbital tissues penetrating the optic nerve canal and causing its trophic disturbances, optic nerve ruptures and secondary glaucoma development in the post-traumatic period, and craniocerebral trauma. The clinical picture of blunt injuries to the organ of vision is diverse. Eye contusion manifests not only as symptoms of visual organ damage but also as changes in the victim's general condition. In addition to pain in the craniofacial region, headaches, dizziness, and some difficulty in convergence are observed on the side of the unharmed eye during the first hours and days. A mixed eye injection is characteristic, subsequently decreasing by the end of the first week and the beginning of the second, if the outcome is favorable. One of the reliable signs of a direct blow to the eye is the Fossius ring (the imprint of the pupil's contour on the corneal endothelium). Direct contusion of the cornea in eye contusion leads to damage to its epithelium: erosion, swelling in deep layers. Corneal erosion causes severe pain and photophobia, as well as marked vision loss. In most victims with blunt eye injuries, hyphema of varying degrees is observed. Characteristic manifestations of eye contusion are subconjunctival hemorrhages, conjunctival tears, iris hyperemia, its rupture or dialysis, hemorrhage into the vitreous body of varying intensity, clouding, subluxation, and dislocation of the lens. There are subconjunctival scleral ruptures characterized by hyphema with pronounced hemorrhages under the conjunctiva, small anterior chamber, pupil displacement towards the scleral rupture, hemorrhage into the vitreous body, and hypotonia. In some cases, eye contusion is combined with orbital contusion, accompanied by hemorrhage in its tissues, which leads to exophthalmos, limitation of eyeball mobility up to complete ophthalmoplegia, and sharp decrease in vision resulting from compression of the orbital part of the optic nerve. Changes occurring in the posterior part of the eye during contusion are divided into early (from one to two months) and late (more than two months). Early signs of contusion include retinal blurring, hemorrhage in the area of the yellow spot and retinal periphery, hemorrhage into the vitreous body, retinal rupture and traumatic detachment, rupture of the choroid, and optic nerve damage. Late complications of eye contusion include post-traumatic chorioretinal dystrophy, traumatic retinal detachment, and optic nerve atrophy. According to various authors, the prognosis for optic nerve atrophy is unfavorable: dystrophic processes in the optic nerve and retina progress steadily: visual acuity in these patients progressively decreases and may eventually reach 0.03 to 0.0. Based on the results of studying and analyzing the clinical symptoms observed in patients with blunt injuries of the visual organ, several authors have concluded that there are symptoms that always lead to long-term or persistent loss of working capacity; these include optic nerve atrophy. The outcome of eye injuries can occur long after the injury - from 6 to 12 months. This is due to the peculiarities of the eyeball's anatomical structure, the prolonged inflammatory and immune processes in the inner membranes of the damaged eye. The first ophthalmological signs of optic nerve atrophy appear several days - several weeks after the injury. However, in the interests of the investigation, it is necessary to conduct a forensic medical examination and determine the degree of loss of general work capacity earlier, without waiting for the outcome of the injury. According to the "Table of Percentage of Persistent Loss of General Working Capacity," injuries to the organs of vision are assessed by forensic medical experts when there are certain consequences of external causes. Among them are: decreased visual acuity, complete loss of vision, narrowing of visual fields - clinical symptoms of optic nerve atrophy, allowing for the qualification of the degree of harm caused to health by this pathology only by these three signs. We believe it is appropriate to cite as an example a case from practice that is interesting

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because during the forensic medical examination, the expert commission had the opportunity to track the victim's visual acuity before the injury, which also served as one of the proofs of the connection between the development of visual atrophy and eye trauma: On July 26, 2009, a 34-year-old citizen S., a well-known man, was inflicted multiple injuries to the face and head with his fist. During the initial forensic medical examination, conducted the day after the injury, character injuries were established. "hemorrhage of the lower lip mucosa to the right, facial hemorrhage, bleeding of the upper extremities, fracture of the crown of the first tooth on the upper jaw to the right," which were assessed as "not causing harm to health" based on their severity.

At the stage of the court investigation, the victim filed a request for a repeat commission forensic medical examination due to her disagreement with the established degree of harm to health and the presence of injury consequences. From the medical record, it follows that upon examination On 27.07.09, the traumatologist noted: contusion of the eyelids of both eyes, hemorrhages in the conjunctiva, pupils are equal, nystagmus. On 31.07.09, she was examined by an ophthalmologist: visual acuity VOS=0.8; VOD=1.0. Objectively: hemorrhages in the mucous membrane of both eyes, under the conjunctiva of the eyeball of the left eye. Optical media are transparent. Eye fundus: slight fullness of blood and curvature of veins. Arteries are narrow. Diagnosis: Contusion of the eyelids of both eyes. Hemorrhages under the conjunctiva. On 02.09.09, the patient repeatedly visited the ophthalmologist with complaints of a floating spot in the left eye, which is associated with the injury on 26.07.09. VOD=1.0. In biomicroscopy: the cornea is transparent. The lens is transparent. In the vitreous body of the left eye, there is a floating shadow. The vitreous body of the right eye is transparent. The diagnosis was established: Destruction of the vitreous body of the left eye (organized partial hemophthalmos of the left eye). According to the results of annual medical examinations, S.'s visual acuity from 2000 to 04.12.2008 was 1.0 for both eyes. In the submitted medical documentation, no other diseases that could cause optic nerve atrophy were recorded. During the commission examination, the patient 26.01.10 was additionally examined: Visual fields were examined, resulting in isolated peripheral scotomas of both eyes, as well as concentric narrowing of the visual field in the left eye up to 50%. During electrophysiological examination, changes within normal limits. Examination of the fundus reveals paleness of the optic disc.

Analysis of the submitted medical documents and the results of additional studies allowed the commission to conclude that S. had a moderate degree of concussion of the left eyeball, hemorrhages in the conjunctiva of the eyeballs, complicated by the development of partial atrophy of the left optic nerve. A direct causal relationship has been established between left eyeball trauma and partial atrophy of the left optic nerve. Correspondingly, the degree of harm caused to health also changed (light harm to health due to insignificant permanent loss of general work capacity less than 10%). Nevertheless, the probability of the disease progressing in this patient is high. Thus, post-traumatic atrophy of the optic nerve, as a complication of eye trauma and craniocerebral trauma, develops some time after injury, therefore, during forensic medical examinations, it is advisable to refer victims for additional examinations (sight acuity and fields, CT and MRI of the brain and eye sockets, etc.), mandatory requests for medical documents containing information about the condition of the visual organs before injury, and to conduct differential diagnostics with other pathological conditions.

Delinquent behavior of adolescents with mental illnesses in new economic conditions is one of the most pressing medical and social problems. One of the most important reasons determining the age-specific nature of asocial adolescent behavior is that we are dealing with a significant age period - puberty.

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